

Behaviour of Chloronitrobenzenes with Hydrazine and Hydrazine Derivatives. Part XII. *2-Phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles and their 1-Oxides

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A few 2-phenyl-1,2,3-benzotriazoles and their 1-oxides have been obtained by interaction of phenylhydrazines and halogenonitrobenzenes. Where formation of more than one triazole is possible, only one triazole has been isolated. Structures to such compounds have been assigned.

In this communication are described a few characteristics of several 2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazoles and their 1-oxides (Tables I and II), obtained by condensing phenylhydrazines with halogenonitrobenzenes. Of these (I a), (I b), and (I c) can possibly yield two 2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazoles, though only one has been isolated in each case. The structure to the products can be assigned by a procedure reported by one of us (Deorha, Agra University Ph.D. thesis, 1953) and subsequently by Joshi and Gupta (this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 681). Thus in case of the product (IIa or IIIa) from 4-chloro-1-bromo-2, 6-dinitro-3-methylbenzene, when the nitro group was substituted by a chlorine atom, the dichloro-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole obtained was found to be identical with 4, 6-dichloro-7-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole, formed similarly from 4-chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole. The structure of the latter follows from its synthesis from 2-chloro-1-bromo-4, 6-dinitro-5-methylbenzene and phenylhydrazine. Therefore the triazole from (I a) must also have the methyl group in position 7 and must be (II a).

- I a : $R_1 = \text{Me}; R_2 = \text{Cl}; X = \text{Br}$.
 I b : $R_1 = \text{Me}; R_2 = \text{Br}; X = \text{Br}$.
 I c : $R_1 = \text{Me}; R_2 = \text{NO}_2; X = \text{Cl}$.
 I d : $R_1 = \text{Cl}; R_2 = \text{Cl}; X = \text{Cl}$.
 I e : $R_1 = \text{Br}; R_2 = \text{Cl}; X = \text{Cl}$.

By condensation of (I d) with phenylhydrazine Walter (*Dissertation*, Freiburg, B, 1889, S28) obtained a 2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole to which he could not assign a definite structure as three isomeric compounds could probably result from the reaction. Identical products are obtained by heating (I d) and (I e) with phenylhydrazine in ethanolic solutions; both of them must therefore be 4: 7-dichloro-6-nitro-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole.

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TABLE I
2-Phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazoles.

Halogenonitrobenzene.	2-Phenylbenzotriazole.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
1-Bromo-4, 6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Nitro-5-methyl-	72%	155°	Buff	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄	N: 21.94%	22.05%
1, 2-Dibromo-4, 6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-Bromo-6-nitro-7-methyl-	45	178°	Light yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 23.88	24.02
2-Chloro-1-bromo-4, 6-dinitro-5-methyl-	4-Chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-	53	155°	Buff	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 12.51	12.30
1, 4-Dibromo-2, 6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Bromo-4-nitro-7-methyl-	54	165°	Sepia	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 23.76	24.02
4-Chloro-1-bromo-2, 6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Chloro-4-nitro-7-methyl-	50	160°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 12.43	12.30
2-Chloro-1-bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-6-nitro-	79	179°	Sepia	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 12.54	12.93
1-Chloro-3-bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	5-Chloro-6-nitro-	69	207°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 13.13	12.93
1, 2, 3-Trichloro-4, 6-dinitro-	4, 5-Dibromo-6-nitro-	80	206°	Cream	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂	Br: 39.82	40.20
2-Chloro-1, 3-dibromo-4, 6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-5-bromo-6-nitro-	82	213°	Light buff	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr	Cl + Br: 32.39	32.67
1, 2, 3-Trichloro-4, 6-dinitro-	4, 5-Dichloro-6-nitro-	84	198°	Buff	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 23.14	22.97
1, 2, 4-Trichloro-3, 5-dinitro-	4, 7-Dichloro-6-nitro-	69	166°	Sepia	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 22.86	22.97
1, 4-Dichloro-2-bromo-3, 5-dinitro-	4, 7-Dichloro-6-nitro-	68	166°	Sepia	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 22.78	22.97

TABLE II
2-Phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole-1-oxides.

Halogenonitrobenzene.	2-Phenylbenzotriazole-1-oxide.	Yield.	M.P.	Colour.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.
4-Chloro-1-iodo-2, 6-dinitro-	6-Chloro-4-nitro-	70%	204°	Golden yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 11.81%	12.22%
1-Bromo-4, 6-dinitro-3-methyl-	6-Nitro-5-methyl-	73	190°	Do	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₄	N: 21.04	20.74
2-Chloro-1-bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-6-nitro-	65	202°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 11.97	12.22
4-Bromo-1-iodo-2, 6-dinitro-	6-Bromo-4-nitro-	72	198°	Golden yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 23.42	23.88
1-Chloro-3-bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	5-Chloro-6-nitro-	68	195°	Fawn	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl	Cl: 12.03	12.22
1, 2, 3-Trichloro-4, 6-dinitro-	4, 5-dibromo-6-nitro-	70	203°	Buff	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br ₂	Br: 39.98	38.64
2-Chloro-1, 3-dibromo-4, 6-dinitro-	4-Chloro-5-bromo-6-nitro-	72	212°	Fawn	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ ClBr	Cl + Br: 31.54	31.25
1, 2, 3-Trichloro-4, 6-dinitro-	4, 5-Dichloro-6-nitro-	71	192°	Light buff	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 21.63	21.84
1, 2, 4-Trichloro-3, 5-dinitro-	4, 7-Dichloro-6-nitro-	68	178°	Light yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 21.52	21.84
1, 4-Dichloro-2-bromo-3, 5-dinitro-	4, 7-Dichloro-6-nitro-	67	178°	Do	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Cl ₂	Cl: 21.71	21.84
1-Chloro-2-bromo-4, 6-dinitro-	4-Bromo-6-nitro-	70	202°	Yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄ Br	Br: 23.51	23.88
1-Chloro-2, 4, 6-trinitro-3-methyl-	4, 6-Dinitro-7-methyl-	69	201°	Dirty yellow	C ₁₃ H ₉ O ₂ N ₄	N: 22.39	22.22

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazoles and their 1-Oxides.—The compounds, described in Tables I and II, were prepared by heating the halogenonitrobenzenes with phenylhydrazine (cf. Joshi and Gupta, *loc. cit.*).

4,6-Dichloro-7-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole.—4-Chloro-6-amino-7-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole, obtained by reduction of 4-chloro-6-nitro-7-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole, was crystallised from ethanol in colorless needles, m.p. 170°. (Found: Cl, 13.94. $C_{13}H_{11}N_4$ Cl requires Cl, 13.73%).

4, 6-Dichloro-7-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole, obtained from the above compound by the replacement of amino group by a chlorine atom, was crystallised from benzene in colorless crystals, m.p. 148°. (Found: Cl, 25.23. $C_{13}H_9N_4Cl_2$ requires Cl, 25.24%).

Similarly 6-chloro-4-nitro-5 (or 7) -methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole gave 6-chloro-4-amino-5 (or 7)-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole which was crystallised from ethanol in light yellow crystals, m.p. 180°. (Found: Cl, 13.82. $C_{13}H_{11}N_4$ Cl requires Cl, 13.73%) and then dichloro- 2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole, m.p. 148°, which was found to be identical with 4,6-dichloro- 7-methyl-2-phenyl-1, 2, 3-benzotriazole.

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